

E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT INFLUENCES ON THE GLOBALIZATION PROCESS

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Abstract. This article talks about the role and factors of e-commerce, which is increasingly developing in the era of globalization, in improving the global economy. It is also given how to create transparency and ease in the development of sectors in the country by implementing this process.

Keywords: e-commerce, globalization, access to markets, exchange of trade and services, logistics and transport, financial operations, marketing and advertising.

Introduction. The impact of the development of e-commerce on the globalization process is huge. E-commerce connects the countries of the world and opens up new opportunities for them. Through this process, it will be possible to facilitate trade transactions between countries, reduce costs, and create opportunities to enter new markets. Through e-commerce, companies will have the opportunity to present themselves in the global market, establish relationships with new customers and provide their services worldwide. Also, through e-commerce, people will be able to buy the products they need and use services around the world. This will strengthen the connections between people through the global network and increase the integration around the world.

No. 392 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated

20.07.2022 "On amendments and additions to some decisions of the government of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the creation of favorable conditions for the improvement of electronic commerce administration and its further development According to the decision:

"Ministry of Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan”:

within two months, make changes to the Regulation on the Fund for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies, taking into account the mechanism of financing state-level socially significant projects in the field of electronic commerce;

in order to ensure the effective functioning of the mechanism of remote identification of customers depending on the mobile number, until the end of 2018, develop and approve the procedure for saving the phone number when the subscriber of the mobile communication network switches to another mobile communication network", - marked as

An unprecedented situation has arisen in the world economy: the economic space has gained a global scale, which has led to a decrease in opportunities for extensive economic growth. Therefore, in the context of a decrease in aggregate demand and a slowdown in economic dynamics, in the new cycle, the distribution sector, and not the production sector, will serve as the driving force for innovation. Where there are untapped markets, manufacturing becomes a priority. In the economy of global surplus production, innovative activity is focused on the place where the demand is concentrated - that is, the sphere of distribution.

The impact of e-commerce on the globalization process can be seen in many ways:

1. Access to Markets: E-commerce expands access to global markets. Through computers, smartphones and the Internet, customers in any

country will have access to the world's markets.

2. Exchange of trade and services: Through e-commerce, products and services can be easily exchanged in world markets. Customers can buy, sell and trade online.

3. Logistics and Transport: E-commerce will further develop the field of logistics and transport. Products and services are delivered easily and quickly, and customers can get the purchased products delivered quickly.

4. Financial transactions: E-commerce makes financial transactions easier and faster. Online payment systems, electronic currencies and other financial instruments make global financial relations even easier.

5. Marketing and Advertising: E-commerce further develops the field of marketing and advertising. It will be possible to establish relationships with customers and implement marketing strategies through Internet advertising, social networks.

Therefore, e-commerce influences the process of globalization and further integrates world markets. This facilitates the exchange of trade and services, accelerates financial transactions and develops marketing and advertising.

In the process of globalization of e-commerce, the exchange of services is facilitated in the following directions:

1. Online Platforms: Online platforms for exchanging services, such as online trading platforms or service marketplaces, provide opportunities to connect customers and service providers. Exchange of services through these platforms will be easy and fast.

2. Electronic payment systems: In e-commerce, payment systems for services, such as online payment platforms or electronic currencies, facilitate payment for services. Customers can purchase services quickly and conveniently by making payments online.

3. Service Marketplaces: In e-commerce, service marketplaces, such as

freelance platforms or service-specific platforms, provide opportunities to connect service providers with customers. Exchange of services through these platforms will be easy and fast.

4. Communication tools: In e-commerce, communication tools, such as e-mail, social networks or online chat services, facilitate communication between service providers and customers. Exchange of services and communication with service providers becomes easy and fast through these tools.

Conclusion. In general, the role of international trade in globalization processes, from its initial stage, is enormous. Therefore, the potential effect caused by Uzbekistan's accession to the Bjsst will be to improve the conditions for protecting the export of products in this short-term period from the obstacles and limitations that occur in the world market. In the long term, however, it was achieved to increase the competitiveness of production at the enterprise on the basis of increasing labor productivity and reducing costs in the domestic and world markets. These situations accelerate the process of structural changes and make it possible to form an export-oriented economic system, grow foreign investments, participate in World Economic Relations. in the globalization process of lektron Commerce, the exchange of services becomes easier and faster. Online platforms, electronic payment systems, services markets and communication tools facilitate the exchange of services.

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